

OXALIS CORNICUALATA: INSIGHTS AND ADVANCES IN THE CHEMISTRY AND BIOLOGY

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INTRODUCTION

For decades natural resources have been a genesis of medicinal plant and healthcare facilities. A number of modern drugs are inspired from natural resources. An enormous portion of world's population depends on historical medicine. In India, the base of treatment system and remedy for several illness is herbal medicine from primordial days¹.

From being regarded as outdated and discredited. Herbs are providing majority of population some of the very important medicine which are used in the modern era as well. There is a belief that herbal medicines are little harmful and free from risk as compared to the synthetic drugs entities in human body. Even researcher of modern medication system has realized the consequences of dietary items, in the form of nutraceuticals and in the treatment of many chronic diseases. The ethno pharmacologists, botanists, microbiologists and natural product researchers are constantly in search of efficacy and mode of action of different medicinal plants and their important medicinal substances as well.²

Oxalis Corniculata Linn. One of the most flexible plants family Oxalidaceae. The name oxalis is derived from the Greek word 'Oxys' meaning sour and This plant is delicate, low growing and herbaceous plant. It exhibits board spectrum of biological potency.³

Commonly known as wood sorrel. Oxalis consist of many bioactive constituents like several alkaloids, flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, saponins, tannins, terpenoids and steroids.⁴ and possess lot of pharmacological and biological activities like wound healing⁵, anti-diarrheal, anti-cancer, antidiabetic, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, anti-ulcer, anti-epileptic, hypolipidemic and anti-implantation and abortifacient property.

FIGURE NO. 1 Biological Activities of *Oxalis Corniculata*

COMPOUND	STRUCTURE	CLASS	PHARMACOLOGICAL PROPERTIES
Oleic Acid		Fatty acid	Anti-inflammatory, Cardiovascular, absorption, nutrient
Linoleic acid		Fatty acid	Essential fatty acid, dietary sources, cardiovascular, antidiabetic
Stearic acid		Fatty acid	Anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, good for healthy skin
Vitamin E acetate		Vitamin E	Anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer
Squalene		Polyunsaturated hydrocarbons	Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory, Anticancer, immune support, detoxifier

Octadecatrienoic acid		<i>Fatty acid</i>	Anticancer, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective,
Stigmasterol		<i>Phytosterol</i>	Anticancer, Anti-inflammatory Lowering cholesterol
Palmitic acid		<i>Fatty acid</i>	Anticancer, Anti-inflammatory
β -Sitosterol		<i>Phytosterol</i>	Anticancer, Anti-inflammatory Lowering cholesterol, prostate Cancer
Luteolin		<i>Natural flavonoid</i>	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, neuroprotective, cardioprotective
Betulins		<i>Triterpenoids</i>	Anticancer, Anti-inflammatory

Apigenin		<i>Flavonoid</i>	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, neuroprotective, cardioprotective
Ethyl gallate		<i>Ester derivative gallic acid</i>	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Antimicrobial
p-hydroxybenzoic acid		<i>Phenolic derivative of benzoic acid</i>	Antioxidant
Syringic acid		<i>Phenolic</i>	Antiinflammatory, Antioxidant, Antimicrobial
Citric acid		<i>Organic acid</i>	Nephroprotective, Improve blood circulation, used in skin health
Oxalic acid		<i>Organic acid</i>	Anti-inflammatory, Anticancer, improve immune health

Isovitexin		<i>c-glycosyl flavones</i>	Anti-inflammatory, Anticancer Antidiabetic, Cardiovascular
Isoorientin		<i>Glycoside</i>	Anticancer, Antioxidant, Hepatoprotective, Antinociceptive
Trimethoxyflavone		<i>flavone</i>	Anticancer, Anti-inflammatory, Antitumor

 Table 1: Various compounds of *Oxalis Corniculata*

***Oxalis Corniculata* in Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM)**

Wood sorrel (Cu Jiang Cao)

Oxalis corniculata is widespread in Asia and is an important weed in countries such as India and China.⁴⁴ Several archaeobotanical reports of *O. corniculata* seed from China. The earliest of these are from the Majiabang culture (hunan, 7000-5800BP) and Daxi culture (Jiangsu).⁴⁵ the use of plants in traditional medicine can perhaps indicate a long association of a plant with human culture⁴⁶.

This highly successful weedy species is so widespread, this is highly successful weedy species is so widespread, particularly in areas disturbed by humans, that its origin is unknown⁴⁷. From China it has been reported in additional provinces, such as Heilongjiang, Jilin, Ningxia and Xinjiang, where it is likely a weed in protected locations, such as in greenhouses. The most frequent encountered variety in China is *Oxalis corniculata*. *Oxalis corniculata* plant's leaves, flowers, seeds and immature green seeds pods are all edible. It is often used in salads, as a seasoning or in a soups or sauces. Oxalis leaves could be used for making a wonderful refreshing tea. The Chinese use of *Oxalis corniculata* which is also called sorrel. It is used to cool, astringe and to treat diarrhea, fever, hemorrhoids, inflammation and scurvy. It can be used to clear heat, supports stomach Yin, to clears damp heat, stops bleeding. Medicinal uses of *Oxalis corniculata*

are to treat Fevers, thirst, sore throat, cold sores, headache, prevent scurvy, sinusitis, congestion, headaches, diarrhea, dysentery, jaundice, kidney stones, gravel, herpes, hemorrhages.

Traditional uses of Oxalis Corniculata

Oxalis Corniculata is an important medicinal plant originating from the tropics and subtropics¹⁰. this has been used as traditional medicine and has been recorded in traditional medicine systems such as Ayurveda, Unani and Siddha. Oxalis corniculata is traditionally used as raw vegetable⁸.

It is also used to treat liver disorders, jaundice, urinary tract⁹ also used to cure influenza, fever, enteritis, diarrhea, sprains, from bites of poisonous snake, traumatic injuries.

Direct infusion of O. Corniculata can help children to get rid of hookworms. It has been also used as anti- scorbatic to treat patients with scurvy.

Infusion of leaves is used to remove opacities of the cornea and is dropped into the eyes for itching lids.

A decoction of leaves is used as a gargle for the mouth^{11,12}.

In Nepal village, Oxalis corniculata is used as medicinal herb¹⁴. *O. corniculata* is mixed is with the leaf bud of *Justicia adathoda L.* and *Maesa macrophylla* is pounded and the juice about 3 times a day is given in gastric troubles.

According to Rehman et al. local inhabitants in Pakistan use of this plant for treating Vitamin C deficiency and bad mouth smell. The plant is used as stimulant and tonic, beneficial in chest pain, convulsions, cramps and inflammatory tumor⁶². Grounded leaves are eaten raw as chutney that act as blood purifier⁶². Juice of leaves applied to open wound relieves pain, for intense headache paste of ground leaves and raw onions applied to forehead to relieve pain⁶³. The plant is used as a good appetizer and as a remover of Kapa, vata and piles⁶⁴.

Phytochemistry

Oxalis corniculata linn plant contain plenty of phytoconstituents such as palmitic acid, tannins a combination of stearic 8-oleic and linolenic acid.

Oxalis corniculata also have amino carbohydrates, glycosides, phytosterols, phenolic compounds, flavonoids, proteins and volatile oil. It also contain tatric acid, acacetin 7,4'- diOMe apigenin, P-hydroxybenzoic acid, Vanillic acid, syringic acid, isoorientin, isovitexin, swertisin, β -sitosterol, botulin, ethylgallate, 5-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxyflavone, 5-hydroxy-3', 4,6, 7,8-pentamethoxyflavone,, 5-hydroxy-3,6,7, 4'-tetra methoxyflavone, apigenin, Corniculatin A

Figure no.2: Structure of different compounds presented in plant

Pharmacological activities

Anticancer activity of oxalis corniculata

In-silico studies revealed that some of the phytochemicals showed inhibition of epidermal growth factor receptor tyrosine kinase (PDB ID:1M17) inhibitor. *In vitro* studies revealed that the hydroalcoholic plant extracts of *Oxalis corniculata* selectively cytotoxic to human hepatocarcinoma (HepG2) cell line with IC_{50} value $30.245 \pm 0.58 \mu\text{g/ml}$.⁵

In- vitro studies explain that Ethanolic Extract of *Oxalis Corniculata* against Ehrlich Ascites Carcinoma cell lines inhibiting the tumor growth in ascitic and solid tumor models and this is supported by the evidence that it may have a tumoricidal effect and thereby it may maintain the normal hematological profile.

EEOC possesses protective action on the hemopoietic system.⁶

In-vitro anticancer activity of organic extracts of *Cynodon dactylon* and methanolic extract *Oxalis corniculata* on HepG2 cell line was shown that it is toxic to HepG2 there is dose

dependent increase in cell death. Real PCR results also showing that in treated cell line also not increasing P53 and PTEN genes, and DNA damaging effects were also not detected in treated cells.⁷

According to valakatte *et.al* cytotoxicity studies on the HCT-116 cell line colorectal cancer cell line have indicated that the extract can inhibit cell proliferation with an IC₅₀ value of 119.498µg/ml

In- silico results signify those two constituents of the extract namely Desulphosinigrin and d-Glycero-d-ido-heptose exhibit strong and specific interactions with the caspase binding site of apoptosis protein -X- linked inhibitor of apoptosis (XIAP). Result shown that these compounds maybe capable of inhibiting XIAP in the cellular environment, thereby promoting apoptosis, resulting in the apoptosis¹¹

Saif MS Ansari *et al* assessed that three extract of *O.corniculata* was taken and tested on HCT116 Cell line i.e. ethanol, aqueous and chloroform extracts. The IC₅₀ results for all three extracts at different concentration showed that chloroform exhibited more effective with IC₅₀ value 47.34±1.24µg/ml. Therefore, the cytotoxic activity of plant *O.corniculata* showed ability to suppress cancer cell¹⁸. Recently, investigation suggested that hydroethanolic extract of *O.corniculata* is also shown effective cytotoxic treatment against Hep-G2 cell lines¹⁹.

In-silico docking study predicted that n-hexadecanoic acid are potential against the cytochrome P450CYP17A1 target receptor protein

	Studies	Phytocompound	Cell lines	Receptor Inhibiting	Action exhibit
Anticancer activity of Oxalis Corniculata	<i>In-silico</i>	Apigenin	HepG2	Epidermal growth factor receptor tyrosine kinase	Anticancer
	<i>In-vitro</i>	Hydroalcoholic plant extract	HepG2	Scavenging free radicals	Cytotoxic
	<i>In-vitro</i>	Ethanollic extract	Ehrlich ascites Carcinoma, solid tumor	Inhibiting tumor growth	Tumoricidal
	<i>In-vitro</i>	Methanolic extract	HepG2	p53 and PTEN genes	Cytotoxic
	<i>In-vitro</i>	Methanolic extract	HepG2	DNA	Anti-cancer
	<i>In-vitro</i>	Methanolic extract	HCT-116	X-linked apoptosis protein	Promoting Apoptosis

				(XIAP)	
	<i>In-silico</i>	Methanolic extract	HCT-116	X-linked apoptosis protein (XIAP)	Promoting Apoptosis

 Table 2: Anticancer activity of *Oxalis corniculata*

Figure no.3 Compounds of oxalis corniculata showing anticancer activity

Antidiabetic activity of oxalis corniculata

Diabetes is a chronic metabolic disorder which is characterized by high levels of blood glucose, mainly due to lack of sensitivity to insulin and dysfunction in pancreatic β -cells. According to Kaushik. S et al (2023) assessed Ethanolic extract of leaves of *Oxalis Corniculata* was effectively normalize the increased levels of blood sugar when compared to standard drug Glibenclamide, study also shown significant reduction in glycogen levels in liver, skeletal muscles and cardiac muscles. It is also seen that it reduces the blood glucose level in Adrenaline induced hyperglycemia, through mechanism antidiabetic activity of Ethanolic extract of leaves of *Oxalis Corniculata* is justified by presence of phytoconstituents, which have got insulin like action or convinced insulin secretion from the β cells or may be enhanced transport of blood glucose to peripheral tissues or might be increased transcription of GLUT4 to the cell membranes¹⁶.

I.kabach et al. assessed that methanolic extract of *O.pes- caprae* flowers reduced significantly both α - amylase and α - glucosidase activities and a protective property against protein glycation. In alloxan-induced diabetic mice, it is shown that administration of the dose 150mg/kg and 250mg/kg of methanolic extract of *O.pes- caprae* flowers after 3 weeks it reduces blood

glucose significantly when compared to glibenclamide indicating that the phenolics compounds present in this extract have potential antihyperglycemic activity¹⁷.

Figure no. 4 Depicting anti-diabetic activity of Oxalis corniculata

Antioxidant Activity

Diseases are believed to be influenced by reactive oxygen species. Free radicals have a harmful role in biological systems, radical scavenging activities are essential. Numerous secondary metabolites, including phenols, polyphenols and flavonoids these are scavengers and antioxidant sources. Many studies have supported the antioxidant activity of *O. corniculata*. In one the study it is evaluated that total antioxidant capacity of hydroalcoholic extract was evaluated by using a variety of methodologies, i.e. (DPPH, nitric oxide scavenging activity, ABTS, FRAP, NBT, ferrous ion chelating activity and TBA). Antioxidant effect is due presence of antioxidants, which have been shown to break the free radical chain by donating a hydrogen molecule. On the basis of experiments performed, it was concluded that plant contains a wide range of secondary metabolites that holds the strong antioxidant activity¹⁹. It is believed that plant possess

antioxidant activity due presence of many phytochemicals such as glycosides, tannins, phytosterols, flavonoids and polyphenols^{23,24}. These molecules shown to scavenge free radicals and reduces oxidative stress^{25,26}.

The methanolic extract of *O. corniculata* showed *in-vivo* antioxidant activity in rat paw edema and cotton pellet induced granuloma formation²⁷. The acidic polysaccharide, is the primary active ingredient in aqueous extract, significantly minimize oxidative damage in cell line HEK-293 and *Caenorhabditis elegans*²⁸.

Antimicrobial Activity

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a growing concern worldwide.⁴⁸

According to recent study, an estimated 4.95 million died from diseases associated with AMR in 2019^{49,50}. The ethanol and Methanol fractions of *O.corniculata* has shown notable effectiveness in tackling *Stapylococcus aureus*⁵¹ and its biofilm formation ability⁵² along with some clinical isolates of *Vibrio cholerae*⁵³, *staphylococci species*, *salmonella typhi*⁵⁴ and some Multi-Drug resistant (MDR) strains of *Citrobacter koseri*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*⁵⁵.

n-butanol and n-hexane soluble fractions of *Oxalis corniculata* also had significant antimicrobial activity for bacterial strains *shigella dysenteriae*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Salmonella typhi* and strain of fungus, *Fusarium solani*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus flexneri*.⁵⁶ Apart from organic extracts, water extract was also effective against *Candida albicans*.⁵⁷ The cream made out of oil

in water-based emulsion and a 20% fresh leaf extract was also effective against bacterial strains of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Neuroprotective Activity

The neuroprotective effect of alcoholic extract of *Oxalis corniculata* was evaluated in the behavioral analysis features in MPTP (1-methyl,4-phenyl 1,2,3,6-tetra hydro pyridine) induced Parkinsonism in mouse. Treatment with *Oxalis corniculata* reversed the alterations in locomotor and muscle coordination in MPTP induced parkinsonic mouse. At different doses of *Oxalis Corniculata* increased memory retention and retrieval significantly⁶⁰. The potential improvement in memory performance by ethanol extract might possibly be described due to the occurrence of flavonoids, coumarins, tocopherols and phenolic acids.

Methanolic Extract of *Oxalis Corniculata* tested on 2 models of depression i.e. Forced swimming test and Tail suspension test. Methanolic extract decreases the duration of immobility and also shown neuroprotective property on depression, due to the presence of the phytochemicals and due to its potent antioxidant property. Phytochemicals which play responsible action were found to be flavonoids, saponins, tannins and polyphenols⁶¹.

Anxiolytic activity

Ethanol extract of *Oxalis corniculata* produce a significant increase in the number of squares crossed, but significantly decreased both the immobility and fecal pellets when compared with control mice. It is also reducing fighting episodes significantly when controlled with control mice. It is also seen that these results were found to be consistent with anxiolytic effect produced by diazepam⁶⁶. Another study indicated a reduction in anxiety-like behavior in the ethanol extract-treated groups. Treatments increased the time spent in the open arm of the elevated plus maze and decreased the number of head dips in the hole board test as compared to the control group⁶⁶. The methanolic extract also showed neuroprotective activity in mice models of depression in the tail suspension test and the swimming test; methanolic extract-treated groups showed a decline in immobility time compared to the control group⁶⁷.

Hepatoprotective activity

The hepatoprotective activity of *Oxalis corniculata* can be attributed to its antioxidative and anti-inflammatory. *Oxalis corniculata* exhibits hepatoprotective effects by enhancing liver detoxification pathways, improving bile secretion, and reducing liver fibrosis. The liver of rats treated with aqueous leaf extract significantly reduced CCl₄-induced increases in serum levels of bilirubin, AST, ALT and ALP. It only showed less damage than the livers of rats treated with

CCl₄⁶⁸. Other study with ethanolic extract showed a membrane -stabilizing effect, which helped protect the liver cells from damage caused by thioacetamide (TAA) in rats.⁶⁹ *In- silico* study, active compounds of *O. corniculata* and 30 potential targets, like TP53, AKT1, ALB and IL6, were employed in network pharmacology and from this study this is concluded that several biological process and signaling pathways potentially involved in the anti-hepatic effects⁷⁰. Methanolic extract of *O.corniculata* (leaf and stem) shown reduction in liver enzyme levels (SGOT,SGPT,GGTP, ALP) and total bilirubin content.

Anti- inflammatory Activity

Inflammation is a complex immune process that occurs as a response in defense when an organism is attacked by various inflammatory stimulus⁷³. *In vivo* inflammatory bowel diseases model displayed significant anti- inflammatory activity when treated with ethanolic extract of *O. Corniculata* leaves in rat⁷². In another animal model ethanolic extract of *O.corniculata* demonstrated anti- inflammatory and analgesic effects in mice with acute peritonitis induced by acetic acid. Apart from ethanolic extract of *O.corniculata*, β - sitosterol isolated using petroleum ether extraction concluded dose dependent anti-inflammatory activity, reducing paw edema in a rat model of carrageenan- induced hind paw edema.

Toxicology of Oxalis Corniculata

An acute oral toxicity was performed in both female and male mice with the methanol extract of *O. Corniculata* according to organization for economic Co-operation and development (OECD) guideline 425. There is no sign of toxicity, mortality and behavioral changes were observed administration of 2000mg/kg b.w. therefore, this is concluded that extract is safe up to 2000 mg/kg^{30, 31}. Following OECD guidelines for the ethanolic extract for acute toxicity concluded those animals survived at 2000mg/kg bodyweight, shown the safety of the ethanolic extract upto 2000 mg/kg.

The hepatotoxicity study was evaluated for aqueous and ethanolic leave decoctions (200 &400 mg/kg) against thioacetamide- induced hepatotoxicity study. This study indicates that oral administration of both decoctions at a dose of 400mg/kg body weight results a distinguished reduction in biochemical parameters like GGTP, SGOT, SGPT, ALP and bilirubin content that were comparatively less than the positive control^{32,33}.

O.corniculata nano-formulation and nano-conjugates

Recently, plant-based synthesis techniques of nanoparticles gained significant interest because of their cheap production, non-toxic nature and eco-friendliness also they are easily applicable to drug delivery, antibiotics, anti-cancer therapy, antidiabetic, and many more³⁴.

S.No	Formulation	Targated cell-lines/ <i>in-vitro</i> / <i>in-vivo</i> / animals used	Approach	Mode of action	Reference
1.	Biogenic copper nanoparticles	Gram -ve E.coli DH5 α and gram	Copper ions can form \rightarrow ROS	Cu ²⁺ ions cross bacterial cell	35,36

	Using Oxalis Corniculata (CuO NPs)	+ve S.aureus	oxidative disruption of nucleic acid and protein Synthesis cell death	membranes and inhibit enzyme activity.	
2.	Biogenic copper nanoparticles Using Oxalis Corniculata (CuO NPs)	STZ induced diabetic Swiss albino mice	Hypoglycemic potential CuO NPs stabilized by phenols, flavonoids, glycosides	Biogenic CuO NP ↓ Blood glucose significantly.	37,38,39, 40
3.	Biogenic silver nanoparticles using Oxalis Corniculata (AgNPs)	Colorectal cancer cell lines HT29 and normal cell lines (L-929)	Cytotoxic effects are due to antineoplastic nature and their ability to cause cell death. There is alterations of cells like reduced size, chromatic condensation and nuclear fragmentation in cancerous cells	Apoptosis induction, Annexin-V	41,42, 43
4.	Oxalis corniculata leaf extract- derived silvern nanoparticles (OCLE-AgNPs)	Gram- positive B.subtilis and Gram- negative E.coli bacterial cells			

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